

WORLD CONGRESS
ON OSTEOPOROSIS,
OSTEOARTHRITIS AND
MUSCULOSKELETAL
DISEASES

AbstractBook

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EVENT

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tremities, as measured by the Srb-LEFS scale (47.00 ± 17.22 vs. 35.83 ± 13.40). However, this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.123$).

Conclusion: As the risk of falling is statistically higher in women with knee osteoarthritis relative to men, this risk factor needs to be considered when developing personalized prevention strategies and designing sex-specific prediction tools for identifying high-risk patient profiles.

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THE INFLUENCE OF OCCUPATIONAL PHYSICAL DEMANDS AND TASK PERFORMANCE MODE ON THE FALL RISK AND THE FUNCTIONAL STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Objective(s) To examine whether in patients with knee osteoarthritis (OA), the fall risk and the functional status differ in relation to the physical and postural demands of occupational tasks.

Material and Methods: This prospective cross-sectional study included 50 patients of both sexes aged 60–75 years that have suffered from knee OA for at least 3 years, with VAS ≥ 5 pain score, treated at the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia. The research was approved by the institutional Ethics Committee and all patients signed an informed consent form before completing a questionnaire comprising sociodemographic data, occupational task performance methods, Morse Fall Scale (MFS) for fall risk assessment, and cross-cultural validation of the Serbian version of the Lower Extremity Functional Scale (Srb-LEFS). Patients with inflammatory rheumatic disease, metabolic disorders of the joints, lower-extremity endoprosthesis, and prior lower-extremity fractures were excluded. Statistical package SPSS ver. 24 was used for all analyses.

Results: The average MFS and LEFS scores for the sample ($M = 69.06 \pm 4.98$ years, 92% women) were 31.30 (SD = 20.87) and 36.72 (SD = 13.87), respectively. Fall risk was lower among individuals that mostly stand at work without bending down/lifting heavy loads (24.38; SD = 20.43) compared to those whose tasks involve bending/lifting loads (32.29; SD = 20.59). The former group had a higher average LEFS score (39.50; SD = 5.53) relative to the latter (35.58; SD = 14.06). However, neither difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.597$; $p = 0.790$).

Conclusion: Although the difference in work performance is not statistically significant, the fall risk is lower and the functional status is better in patients with knee OA whose occupation involves standing but does not require bending/lifting. Thus, strategies for mitigating the risk factors predisposing them to more pronounced knee OA are necessary.

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DISEASE ACTIVITY AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS RECEIVING BIOLOGICAL THERAPY

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Objective: To examine the relationship between disease activity and quality of life in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) treated with biological drugs.

Material and methods: With the approval of the Ethics Committee of the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia (14/01-1/1-25), a retrospective analysis of data spanning a 5-decade period pertaining to 39 RA patients that had received biological therapy was performed. General sociodemographic data, illness duration, biological drug (anti-TNF inhibitors) treatment length, Disease Activity Score (DAS28), and the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ) index were analyzed using the SPSS ver. 24 commercial software.

Results: The average HAQ and DAS28 value for the sample (comprising 71.8% women) was 0.85 ± 0.51 and 3.30 ± 1.00 , respectively. In terms of disease activity, 33.3% of respondents were in remission, 30.8% had low disease activity, 35.9% had moderate disease activity, and none had high disease activity. A statistically significant negative correlation between disease duration and DAS28 score ($p = 0.043$) and well as biological treatment length ($p = 0.029$) was noted. DAS28 = 4.35 ± 0.29 was obtained for patients with RA duration below 5 years, while those who have been ill for 6–10 years scored 2.80 ± 0.91 . Similarly, DAS28 scores of 2.43 ± 0.73 and 3.50 ± 0.96 were attained by those receiving biological drugs for more than 5 years and up to 12 months, respectively. On the other hand, the correlation between disease activity and HAQ index was statistically significant and positive ($r = 0.618$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that quality of life declines with greater disease activity.

Conclusion: In RA patients, disease activity declines with the biological therapy duration. However, higher disease activity is associated with worse quality of life.